

COUPLING EFFECTS OF TEMPERATURE AND FATIGUE, CREEP-FATIGUE INTERACTION AND THERMO-MECHANICAL LOADING CONDITIONS ON CRACK GROWTH AND DOMINANT FAILURE MECHANISMS OF A NICKEL-BASED ALLOY

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This study presents analysis and evaluation of a range of isothermal and non-isothermal experimental crack growth data generated by four type tests carrying out under stress-controlled pure fatigue, creep-fatigue interaction, in-phase (IP) and out-of-phase (OOP) thermo-mechanical fatigue (TMF) conditions. The tests have been carried out using stress cycles with a trapezoidal or triangular waveform and a temperature range of 400–650°C for XH73M nickel-based alloy. As a result of the tests performed, it was found that from the crack growth acceleration point of view, the levels of influence on the alloy's final fracture mechanisms are in the following order: isothermal creep-fatigue interaction, non-isothermal in-phase thermo-mechanical fatigue, isothermal pure fatigue and non-isothermal out-of-phase thermo-mechanical fatigue. The ordering of the crack growth rate curves is supported by detailed fractographic analysis.

Keywords: Creep-fatigue interaction, Thermo-mechanical fatigue, Damage mechanisms, Nickel-based alloy

INTRODUCTION

Heat-resistant alloys have been successfully used in aero-engines and power engineering turbine disks for decades. Crack propagation is a major issue that have to meet certification requirements in terms of damage tolerance service operation and residual fatigue lifetime assessment. The crack growth behaviour under high temperatures have been extensively studied in the past by theoretical, experimental and numerical investigations under different isothermal and thermomechanical conditions. Studies of Stekovic et al. [1], Palmer et al. [2], Jones [3], Li et al. [4], Eckmann and Schweizer [5], Jiang et al. [6] focused on testing methods. Researches of Gayda and Miner [7], Onofrio et al. [8], Pineau et al. [9] have been directed toward experimentally investigating the crack initiation and propagation with microstructure analyses of thermal resistance nickel-based alloys at isothermal fatigue test conditions. Pretty et al. [10], Palmert et al. [11], Jones et al. [12], Norman et al. [13], Segersall et al. [14] carried out extensive tests to assess the effect of phase angle deviation on the dominant crack failure mechanisms under TMF conditions. Feulvarch et al. [15], Karabela et al. [16], Xu et al. [17], Jiang et al. [18], Evans et al. [19] have performed the microstructural investigations of oxygen diffusion effect on crack growth under thermo-cycling conditions. Fessler et al. [20] have found the relation between crack growth behaviour and crack front morphology.

To the knowledge of the authors no significant work has been carried out on the crack growth rate comparison for separate loading conditions like pure fatigue and TMF depending on dominant failure mechanisms. Therefore aim of the present study is analysis and evaluation of a range of isothermal and non-isothermal experimental crack growth data generated by four type tests

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carrying out by stress-controlled pure fatigue (IF), creep-fatigue interaction (CFI), in-phase (IP) and out-of-phase (OOP) thermo-mechanical fatigue (TMF) conditions. The tests have been carried out using cycles with a trapezoidal and triangular waveform and a temperature range of 400–650°C. The crack growth rate tests are supported by detailed observation of the fracture surfaces morphology and analysis of the transition between transgranular and intergranular dominant failure mechanisms.

MATERIAL, TEST SETUP AND LOADING CONDITIONS

The material used in the tests is heat-resistant XH73M nickel-based alloy, which is used for a gas turbine engine’s turbine disc and operates at elevated temperatures with the occurrence of creep conditions. The chemical composition and the main mechanical properties of analysed material at both the ambient and elevated temperature are summarized in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. In Table 2 E is Young's modulus, σ_0 is yield stress, σ_u is tensile strength, δ is elongation, ψ is reduction of area, B_{cr} and n are the Norton creep constant and exponent. For materials in which secondary creep dominates, deformation behavior is described by the Norton elastic-nonlinear viscous constitutive relation

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\dot{\sigma}}{E} + \dot{\epsilon} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{ref}} \right)^n; \quad \dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\dot{\sigma}}{E} + B_{cr} \sigma^n; \quad B_{cr} = \dot{\epsilon}_0 / \sigma_{ref}^n \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ref} is a reference stress, $\dot{\epsilon}_0$ is a reference creep strain rate.

TABLE 1 Chemical composition of XH73M alloy

C	Cr	Mo	Al	Ti	Nb	Ni
0.03-0.07	13.0-16.0	2.8-3.2	1.45-1.8	2.35-2.75	1.9-2.2	basis

TABLE 2 Main mechanical static properties for XH73M alloy

T [°C]	σ_u [MPa]	σ_0 [MPa]	E [GPa]	δ [%]	ψ [%]	B_{cr} [MPa ⁻ⁿ *h ⁻¹]	n
23	1298.25	904.04	215.77	34.94	54.19	-	-
400	1229.53	830.50	192.87	32.31	50.88	2.5*10 ⁻¹¹	2.50
550	1205.93	836.42	206.18	27.73	30.12	4.0*10 ⁻¹²	3.53
650	1079.30	866.05	192.76	10.67	18.35	2.1*10 ⁻¹⁶	4.80
750	839.85	705.46	161.39	8.27	17.90	4.0*10 ⁻²⁶	8.85

Pure fatigue and thermo-mechanical fatigue in-phase tests and pre-crack operations were conducted in a Zwick/Roell HA100 servo hydraulic test machine equipped with an induction heating system including a cylindrical copper coil with its centre axis coinciding with the specimen centre axis. The Zwick/Roell HA100 setup is displayed in Fig. 1. To even out the temperature distribution and assist cooling, compressed air flow directed towards the specimen through three

nozzles was used, positioned circumferentially with equal angular spacing and the same distance to the specimen, as well as at the same vertical position as the notch. The creep–fatigue interaction tests were performed with high-precision crack opening displacement extensometer and a high-temperature three-zone oven.

For the pure isothermal fatigue, creep-fatigue interaction tests and thermo-mechanical fatigue loading conditions, the single edge notched tension (SENT) specimens were employed. The specimen geometry is displayed in Fig. 1c. All specimens used in this study were extracted from the forged disc in an area where the microstructure is rather homogeneous. The specimens were manufactured through turning and wire electrical discharge machining, without application of any additional surface finishing process.

FIGURE 1 (a) Zwick/Roell TMF test equipment; (b) rectangular inductive coil; (c) SENT sample.

This study presents interpretation and evaluation of a range of isothermal and non-isothermal experimental crack growth data generated by four type tests carrying out by stress-controlled fast and slow isothermal fatigue (IF), isothermal creep-fatigue interaction (CFI) and in-phase (IP) and out-of-phase (OOP) thermo-mechanical fatigue (TMF) conditions as it shown in Fig. 2.

Tempe rature	Isothermal			Non-isothermal	
Loading type	Fatigue fast isothermal	Fatigue slow isothermal	Creep + fatigue interaction isothermal	TMF in-phase	TMF out-of- phase (-180°)
Cycles form					
T [°C]	23	400, 650	400, 650	400–650–400	400–650–400
f [Hz]	1.0	0.017	0.014	0.014	0.014

FIGURE 2 Test program for isothermal and thermo-mechanical fatigue conditions.

Tests on SENT specimens are carried out under loads sufficiently below the yield stress of Ni-based alloy with an initial fatigue crack obtained at room temperature. The pure fatigue tests were performed at ambient 23°C and elevated temperature 150°C, 400°C and 650°C with an applied nominal stress asymmetry ratio of $R = 0.1$ under loading at a frequency of 0.017 and 1.0 Hz. The creep-fatigue interaction crack growth rate tests were carried out at elevated temperature 400°C and 650°C with the same stress asymmetry ratio of $R = 0.1$ in a specially designed the trapezoidal cycle program with the 5-s loading and unloading parts and dwell time of 60 s, which was applied at the maximum load, as can be seen in Fig. 2. The IP and OOP TMF test parameters employed for the single edge notched specimen is a triangle waveform with ratio of $R = 0.1$ at a loading frequency 0.014Hz over a 400-650°C temperature range with heating and cooling rates at 8.3°C/s.

During the thermo-mechanical test, direct measurements of the load-line displacement were carried out using capacitive high-temperature strain gauges. The potential drop (PD) methods, was used to measure the current crack size under the fatigue and creep-fatigue types of loading. Crack length on the outer surface of SENT specimen is measured by using of an optical microscope. By means of a Merlin Zeiss scanning electron microscope (SEM) images, the fracture surface characteristics of the investigated specimens that have been tested under triangular and program loading with temperature variation over a wide range of values were analysed.

FRACTURE SURFACES AND DOMINANT FAILURE MECHANISMS

In the subsequent analysis of the morphology of fracture surfaces and the dominant failure mechanisms, we will follow the sequence of isothermal and thermomechanical fatigue loading conditions, which are shown in Fig.2.

Isothermal fatigue

First of all, we will consider the conditions of isothermal fatigue at ambient ($T=23^\circ\text{C}$) and elevated temperatures ($T=400^\circ\text{C}$, 650°C). Backscattered scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the crack path in IF at room temperature, showing transgranular morphology with ductile fatigue striations are given in Fig.3.

FIGURE 3 Fractography of isothermal fatigue at ambient temperature (a) near pre-crack, (b) mid crack and (c) near final failure.

Clear evidence of this is displayed on the smooth fracture surfaces with cleavage steps, river patterns and feather markings typical of transgranular growth. For the same set of experiments plastic wake and transition from small to extensive scale yielding with increasing of the crack

length can be evidenced. The effect of loading frequency was not noticed by comparing triangular 0.017 Hz and 1.0 Hz cycles.

Observations on SEM images for the moderate high temperature of 400°C, shows that in general XH73M nickel-based alloy seems to fracture predominantly in a transgranular manner, although there is evidence of mixed mode fracture where cracking interacts with interfacial boundaries. The higher temperature of 650°C sees a complete change in the damage mechanism, this time giving rise to an intergranular dominant failure without striations. In agreement to what is often reported for nickel base superalloys in the literature, the conducted IF tests tend to intergranular growth which is consistent with the general observation of increased tendency for intergranular dominant fracture with increasing temperatures under isothermal conditions.

Out-of-phase thermo-mechanical fatigue

This information is to provide more detailed comparison of the morphology for IP and OOP TMF test results on the same XH73M nickel-based alloy using SENT specimens. Fractographic analysis of specimen surfaces tested under 400°C–650°C OOP TMF conditions showed that there are distinctive features of crack growth which require separate consideration.

FIGURE 4 Fractograph showing the transition from intergranular fracture to mixed transgranular-ductile dimples of a dominant failure mechanism under 400–650°C OOP TMF cycle.

Firstly, observations have shown that in the same tested sample, with increasing crack length, three dominant fracture mechanisms are consistently implemented. These findings are supported by Fig. 4, that represents intergranular fracture in the early stage of crack growth (Fig. 4a), then transitions to transgranular dominant failure is observed at the stable Paris section of the fatigue fracture diagram (Fig. 4b), which lastly lead to mixed transgranular-ductile dimples of a dominant

failure mechanism under OOP TMF cycle (Fig. 4d). Secondly, in Fig. 4c a high number of micro-cracks around the large crack are observed on the fracture surface of SENT specimen for OOP TMF testing conditions. As shown on this SEM image, these cracks are located in a vertical plane, which coincides with the direction of action of the applied load to the sample. These micro-cracks being either initiated at the fracture surface or with an obvious distance to this plane. It is worth mentioning that the shape of most of micro-cracks could be associated to transgranular damage mechanism. Detailed view on Fig.4c evidences the micro-cracks distribution, in which the major crack is prone to primary grow.

When considering the major crack to micro-crack coalescence, it is important to note that the 3D stress components distributions play a key role in that process. To illustrate the above features, FEM simulations may be considered for a high temperature SENT test on XH73M Ni-based alloy. The SENT specimen is of 20 mm wide and has a crack length a of about 5 mm. In previous research of the authors [21], for determining the 3D effect on the crack tip fields, the behaviour of stress at the crack front along the specimen thickness direction for IP and OOP TMF test conditions, were analysed.

FIGURE 5 Hoop (a), radial (b) and transversal (c) elastic-plastic stress distributions along crack front toward the thickness direction in SENT specimen for OOP TMF at 400°C - 650°C.

As a reference [21], the distributions of the hoop σ_θ , radial σ_r and transversal σ_z stress along the crack front from the free surface to the mid-plane section are plotted in Fig. 5 for the SENT specimen. The figure shows the behaviour of the elastic-plastic stresses for combinations of normalised crack tip radius values of $r/a = 0.0026$, with variations in the OOP TMF cycling time points. The stress distributions are presented as a function of the normalised specimen thickness z/B for the crack size $a = 15$ mm (where z and B here are specimen thickness and width, respectively). In these figures, $z/B = 0.05$ is the approximate crack front position on the outer border of the specimen, whereas $z/B = 0.5$ is the mid-plane section of the crack front in the SENT specimen.

As expected, the maximum tensile or compressive stresses at different time points under OOP cycles were localised along the crack front over the sample thickness, with significant stress gradients close to the free surface of the specimen. In Fig. 5, the stress components monotonically increased with cycling time from 10 s to 30 s during the first part of the loading cycle, that is corresponding to the state of loading/cooling sequence. For the second part of the OOP TMF cycle at the timing 40 s, 50 s and 0 s was observed the stress decreasing during unloading/heating stage. It follows from the results of the calculations for the OOP TMF cycles that the radial stresses along the crack front are comparable in magnitude to the transversal stresses at the corresponding time points and are approximately two times less than the hoop stresses. Stress distributions like this suggested that high values of elastic-plastic radial stresses cause the appearance of a large number of vertical microcracks and several major cracks.

Transitions between transgranular and intergranular dominant failure mechanisms

This section will present an analysis of the effects of increasing test temperature on the dominant failure mechanisms for isothermal fatigue and fatigue-creep interaction, as well as for in-phase and out-of-phase thermomechanical loading. We will consider data for isothermal conditions at test temperatures of $T=400^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T=650^{\circ}\text{C}$ and thermomechanical fatigue in the temperature range $T=400^{\circ}\text{C}-650^{\circ}\text{C}$ in each deformation cycle.

FIGURE 6 Transgranular fracture with ductile striations for IF (a) and CFI (b) at 400°C , OOP TMF (c) at $400^{\circ}\text{C} - 650^{\circ}\text{C}$; typical intergranular fracture for IF (d) and CFI (e) at 650°C , IP TMF (f) at $400^{\circ}\text{C} - 650^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figures 6(a-c) represent the fracture surfaces for isothermal fatigue, creep-fatigue interaction and out-of-phase TMF cycles at test temperature $T=400^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T=400^{\circ}\text{C}-650^{\circ}\text{C}$ consequently. It

should be noted that for OOP TMF cycle, the computed maximum of von Mises effective stress level is reached at timing $t = 30$ s and temperature $T = 400^\circ\text{C}$. Thus, it would be good reason to compare the data for OOP TMF state with crack growth characteristics at the temperature $T = 400^\circ\text{C}$ of the isothermal fatigue tests at temperature of $T = 400^\circ\text{C}$ and from the creep fatigue interaction tests run at the same temperature. In its turn, Figs. 6(d-f) display the morphology of fracture surfaces for isothermal fatigue, creep-fatigue interaction and in-phase TMF cycles at test temperature $T = 650^\circ\text{C}$ and $T = 400^\circ\text{C} - 650^\circ\text{C}$ respectively.

A change in the crack growth mechanism is observed in Fig.6 with increasing temperature from $T = 400^\circ\text{C}$ to $T = 650^\circ\text{C}$ for isothermal test conditions. Both pure fatigue and creep-fatigue interaction cycles at test temperature $T = 400^\circ\text{C}$ lead to a fully transgranular fracture with ductile striations conditions (Fig. 6a,b). In Fig. 6d,e you can see that at temperature $T = 650^\circ\text{C}$ the intergranular failure mechanism dominates. Moderately elevated temperature $T = 400^\circ\text{C}$ induces cyclic transgranular crack growth across the polycrystalline grain structure. In the case of creep-fatigue interaction, the lower temperature of 400°C sees a complete change in the damage mechanism with respect to elevated temperature 650°C . At the test temperature of 400°C rise to a transgranular dominant failure (Fig. 6b), with striations now more visible as the effect of oxidation and creep is reduced. In contrast, under test temperature $T = 650^\circ\text{C}$ it is observed that intergranular crack growth dominates and the grain structure is clearly defined as the crack has progressed along the grain boundaries.

For the same test temperature range $T = 400^\circ\text{C} - 650^\circ\text{C}$ similar difference in crack path morphology between IP and OOP TMF crack growth was observed. In agreement to what is often reported for nickel base superalloys in the literature, the conducted OOP TMF tests (Fig. 6c) are more transgranular while IP TMF tests (Fig. 6f) tend to manifest intergranular dominant failure mechanism. As expected, IP tests continue to be dominated by intergranular crack growth. Based on the crack path morphology, the influence of oxygen diffusion on the distinction between the crack growth in XH73M Ni-based alloy for tests performed at temperature $T = 400^\circ\text{C}$ and $T = 650^\circ\text{C}$ cannot be completely ruled out at this point. Previous research has demonstrated that oxygen is not necessarily needed to cause intergranular deformation at elevated temperatures. Consequently, it is possible that the difference in crack path morphology between OOP and IP TMF is a result of changes in the crack tip deformation behaviour of the microstructure between 400°C and 650°C , regardless of the role of oxygen. On the other hand, the above argument is opposed by the observed difference in studies Pretty et al. [10] and Jones et al. [12] where oxidation was shown to significantly influence crack growth rates and was easily identified from a transition from transgranular to intergranular cracking. In the present study, we are of the opinion that significant levels of oxygen, capable of influencing fracture behaviour through environmental effects are unable to penetrate to the crack tip when the minimum load with asymmetry ratio $R = 0.1$ is applied at the peak cycle temperature $T = 650^\circ\text{C}$ in the OOP TMF test.

More importantly, it is also found that the propensity to ductile striation morphology of crack growth decreases with increasing test temperature, which indicates a dependency of the dominant failure mechanism on the current crack tip cyclic elastic-plastic stress-strain state. Based on analysis of coupling effects of environment and type of cyclic loading it is concluded that the difference between dominant fracture mechanisms in XH73M Ni-based alloy originates from temperature effects rather than the mechanical conditions at the crack tip. It is obvious that the effect of temperature increase suppresses differences in the dominant failure mechanisms depending on the type of isothermal and non-isothermal mechanical loading.

FATIGUE STRIATIONS AND CRACK GROWTH RATE CHARACTERISTICS

One of the most indicative characteristics of the fracture surfaces state under cyclic loading is the morphology of ductile striations. The profile height and wave size of a periodic structure are quantitative characteristics of cyclic fracture processes. It should be noted that striations appear and grow at certain stages of cyclic fracture and occupy different areas of the tested specimen fracture surface. Under certain combinations of temperature, environmental conditions, level and frequency of applied load, and material properties, striations are not observed throughout the fatigue life. In other words, cyclic loading is not an unambiguous condition for the formation of fatigue striations. In the present study, ductile striations were observed at test temperatures of 23°C and 400°C at certain stages of isothermal fatigue, fatigue-creep interaction, as well as during out-of-phase thermomechanical fatigue cycle in the temperature range 400°C-650°C. When IP TMF is compared to OOP TMF a considerable change in damage mechanism arises. The fatigue striations were completely absent during in-phase TMF cycles in the same test temperature range 400°C-650°C.

The employment of a Merlin Zeiss SEM made it possible to measure the space of fatigue striations along the length of the crack. The results of these measurements for XH73M Ni-based alloy are presented in Fig. 7 for various loading conditions and the level of applied nominal stresses. A transgranular dominant crack is observed under isothermal fatigue conditions with a large number of striations present within the microstructure, shown in Fig. 6a. The spacing between observed ductile striations (Fig. 7a) were measured and found to increase significantly from start to finish from about 0.05 to 4 µm as the crack progressed at an increasing pace. When the test temperature increased from 23°C to 400°C and the level of nominal stresses from 160MPa to 220MPa, an intensive increase in the striation spacings was mentioned.

FIGURE 7 Ductile fatigue striation spacing as a function of crack length for (a) IF at 23°C and 400°C; (b) OOP TMF at 400°C - 650°C for different applied nominal stress level.

The morphology of the OOP TMF fracture surfaces demonstrates transgranular dominant failure mechanism, and therefore, for the stage of stable crack growth in the linear part of the fatigue fracture diagram, it became possible to measure of the striation spacing, the results of which are shown in Fig. 7b. It is obvious that for the temperature range 400°C-650°C, the spacing of the

striations increases significantly when the value of the nominal stresses changes from 150 MPa to 220 MPa.

Previous studies have established that striations appear and grow when certain conditions are met, one of which is cyclic plastic deformation at the crack tip. Thus, it appears as if plastic deformation associated with the crack tip is accommodated by plastic deformation within the grain in OOP TMF crack growth, while deformation in terms of grain boundary sliding seems more justified in IP TMF crack growth. It's obvious that the IP case demonstrates low amount of deformation, whereas the OOP case indicates severe deformation.

In studies Shanyavsky [22,23] was noted a direct relationship between the striation spacings on the microscale and the macrocrack growth rate therefore, it will be useful to compare with each other the fatigue failure diagrams of XH73M Ni-based alloy for the loading conditions under consideration, taking into account the manifestation of the dominant failure mechanisms. To this end, Fig. 8a shows the fatigue fracture diagrams in terms of the elastic stress intensity factor (SIFs) for the XH73H nickel alloy SENT specimens for the conventional triangular and trapezoidal cycles, which consists of the dwell time of 60 s and loading/unloading time of 5 s for each loading cycle (Fig.2). It was observed that for the isothermal high temperature test of $T=650^{\circ}\text{C}$ the crack growth rate (CGR) during creep-fatigue interaction increased by approximately one order of magnitude with respect to the pure isothermal fatigue loading conditions. It is obvious that for the test temperature $T=650^{\circ}\text{C}$, both environmentally assisted crack growth and creep damage can accelerate crack growth (compared to isothermal fatigue crack growth data at peak temperature). This conclusion is confirmed by fractographic observation that the acceleration of crack growth rates observed here result of intergranular dominant failure mechanism (Figs. 6 d,e). Lowering the test temperature to $T=400^{\circ}\text{C}$ leads to a decrease in the crack growth rate both under pure fatigue and creep-fatigue interaction conditions by about two and a half orders of magnitude. For these conditions of cyclic deformation, the transgranular mechanism is dominant (Figs. 6 a,b).

FIGURE 8 Comparison of fatigue fracture diagrams in terms of elastic SIFs for IF and CFI (a), IP, OOP TMF and CFI (b), IP, OOP TMF and IF(c) at different temperatures.

The behaviour in the experimental CGR diagrams of nickel alloy XH73H for isothermal ($T=400^{\circ}\text{C}$, 650°C) creep-fatigue interaction and IF and OOP TMF conditions are given in Fig.8b. A comparison of fatigue fracture diagrams in Fig.8b again shows that for the isothermal elevated

temperature test of $T=650^{\circ}\text{C}$ the CGR during creep–fatigue interaction exceeds by approximately one order and more of magnitude with respect to the IP TMF loading with maximal cycle temperature of $T=650^{\circ}\text{C}$. The dominant failure mechanism involved in IP TMF crack growth showing intergranular morphology present similarities with creep-fatigue interaction, consistently with observed high fatigue crack growth rate in both cases. In the tests considered, a significant difference was noted in the crack growth rate between the IP TMF and the OOP TMF tests for the same temperature range (Fig. 8b). In contrast to the IP TMF results, the behaviour of the CGR diagram for OOP TMF conditions with minimal cycle temperature of $T=400^{\circ}\text{C}$ shows approximately the same CGR as creep–fatigue interaction at isothermal test temperature $T=400^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the same transgranular dominant failure mechanism.

Figure 8c represents CGR versus the elastic SIF for the SENT specimen of nickel alloy XH73H for isothermal pure fatigue ($T=23^{\circ}\text{C}$, 400°C , 650°C) and IP and OOP TMF conditions at elevated temperature range of 400°C – 650°C . It was observed that when phase angles 180° for the OOP TMF loading was applied, the contribution of out-of-phase cyclic loading decreased the CGR by approximately one order and more of magnitude compared with the IP TMF cycling. Another observable feature in Fig. 8c is that the crack growth rate for OOP TMF is moderately higher compared to isothermal pure fatigue at the same temperature and nominal stress values. The IP and OOP TMF fracture surfaces (Fig.6c and Fig.6f) agree with results plotted in Fig.8c where it is clear that IP leads to faster growth rates than OOP. This is a result of the change in dominant failure mechanism from IP to OOP as intergranular to transgranular.

CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue fracture diagrams provide a general understanding of the competitive effects of the interactions between isothermal and nonisothermal temperature distributions and cyclic mechanical loads. The assessment of these effects on CGR characteristics depends on the cyclic thermomechanical loading history and material properties at elevated temperatures.

Comparison the growth rates of the two variants under TMF conditions shows that, there is a similar trend to that observed in the isothermal conditions. It can be concluded that OOP TMF cycles are more sensitive to changes in the combination of the applied stress and temperature profile during the deformation cycle.

The variant with intergranular dominant failure mechanism at elevated temperature $T=650^{\circ}\text{C}$ displays higher crack growth rate with respect to the results at moderate temperature $T=400^{\circ}\text{C}$ that is indicated on transgranular dominant cyclic fracture.

As a result of the tests performed, it was found that from the crack growth acceleration point of view, the levels of influence on the alloy's final fracture mechanisms are in the following order: isothermal creep-fatigue interaction, non-isothermal in-phase thermo-mechanical fatigue, isothermal pure fatigue and non-isothermal out-of-phase thermo-mechanical fatigue.

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